

Revisiting pangenome openness with k -mers

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Supplementary Material

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S1 Fitting Heaps' law

Figure S1. Adjusted R^2 values for the fitting of **Pangrowth**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S2. Adjusted R^2 values for the fitting of **Roary**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S3. Adjusted R^2 values for the fitting of **Pantools**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S4. Adjusted R^2 values for the fitting of **BPGA**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S5. Estimated value of α for **Pangrowth**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S6. Estimated value of α for **Roary**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S7. Estimated value of α for **Pantools**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

Figure S8. Estimated value of α for **BPGA**, over different starting points. A minimum of 6 genomes was required to fit the data.

S2 Pangrowth

Figure S9. Average growth of *Bacillus cereus*.

Figure S10. Average growth of *Buchnera aphidicola*.

Figure S11. Average growth of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

Figure S12. Average growth of *Clostridium botulinum*.

Figure S13. Average growth of *Coxiella burnetii*.

Figure S14. Average growth of *Francisella tularensis*.

Figure S15. Average growth of *Helicobacter pylori*.

Figure S16. Average growth of *Prochlorococcus marinus*.

Figure S17. Average growth of *Rhodospseudomonas palustris*.

Figure S18. Average growth of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Figure S19. Average growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

Figure S20. Average growth of *Yersinia pestis*.

S3 Roary

Figure S21. Average growth of *Bacillus cereus*.

Figure S22. Average growth of *Buchnera aphidicola*.

Figure S23. Average growth of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

Figure S24. Average growth of *Clostridium botulinum*.

Figure S25. Average growth of *Coxiella burnetii*.

Figure S26. Average growth of *Francisella tularensis*.

Figure S27. Average growth of *Helicobacter pylori*.

Figure S28. Average growth of *Prochlorococcus marinus*.

Figure S29. Average growth of *Rhodospseudomonas palustris*.

Figure S30. Average growth of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Figure S31. Average growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

Figure S32. Average growth of *Yersinia pestis*.

S4 Pantools

Figure S33. Average growth of *Bacillus cereus*.

Figure S34. Average growth of *Buchnera aphidicola*.

Figure S35. Average growth of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

Figure S36. Average growth of *Clostridium botulinum*.

Figure S37. Average growth of *Coxiella burnetii*.

Figure S38. Average growth of *Francisella tularensis*.

Figure S39. Average growth of *Helicobacter pylori*.

Figure S40. Average growth of *Prochlorococcus marinus*.

Figure S41. Average growth of *Rhodospseudomonas palustris*.

Figure S42. Average growth of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Figure S43. Average growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

Figure S44. Average growth of *Yersinia pestis*.

S5 BPGA

Figure S45. Average growth of *Bacillus cereus*.

Figure S46. Average growth of *Buchnera aphidicola*.

Figure S47. Average growth of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

Figure S48. Average growth of *Clostridium botulinum*.

Figure S49. Average growth of *Coxiella burnetii*.

Figure S50. Average growth of *Francisella tularensis*.

Figure S51. Average growth of *Helicobacter pylori*.

Figure S52. Average growth of *Prochlorococcus marinus*.

Figure S53. Average growth of *Rhodospseudomonas palustris*.

Figure S54. Average growth of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Figure S55. Average growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

Figure S56. Average growth of *Yersinia pestis*.

S6 Histograms

Figure S57. Percentage of items in *Bacillus cereus*.

Figure S58. Percentage of items in *Buchnera aphidicola*.

Figure S59. Percentage of items in *Campylobacter jejuni*.

Figure S60. Percentage of items in *Clostridium botulinum*.

Figure S61. Percentage of items in *Coxiella burnetii*.

Figure S62. Percentage of items in *Francisella tularensis*.

Figure S63. Percentage of items in *Helicobacter pylori*.

Figure S64. Percentage of items in *Prochlorococcus marinus*.

Figure S65. Percentage of items in *Rhodospseudomonas palustris*.

Figure S66. Percentage of items in *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Figure S67. Percentage of items in *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

Figure S68. Percentage of items in *Yersinia pestis*.

